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BIG DATA
OCEAN

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D8.4 – Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report and Plan for Second Reporting Period

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Executive Summary

This document reports the dissemination and communication plans for the second reporting period of the BigDataOcean project. It starts by analysing the activities and strategies accomplished during the first reporting period, as well as the targets then defined. The new plans and indicators proposed in this document are based on this analysis, where new activities are defined, and correcting measures determined when required.

The main results and conclusions for dissemination and communication are the following:

- **Dissemination:** Most goals defined for the first reporting period have been achieved and some even surpassed. Dissemination mechanisms D1 "Organisation of project events", D2 "Participation to conferences and workshops", and D5 "Collaboration and synergies with projects", have presented excellent indicators overcoming all the milestones initially defined for the period. Yet, some specific activities require more attention during the second reporting period, e.g. the number of publications in scientific journals or industrial magazines was not as expected, although this is considered natural as no consolidated results were yet available, and the focus of dissemination was set on publications on fast channels, namely conferences. For the second period, activities such as webinars and training sessions, or to foster participation in standardisation bodies' meetings will have to be started or improved.
- **Communication:** Like the previous item, most of the pre-defined goals were achieved and surpassed. To highlight, the number of unique visits to the website (> 2500) covering most of the World map. Yet, one major conclusion is the need to appoint a social media coordinator among the project teams' members. Dimitris Zisis from EXMILE has been appointed as this is fundamental for providing a dynamic presence in social media, fostering internal and external communication.

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List of Acronyms

BDO	BigDataOcean
DoA	Document of Agreement
Dx.y	Deliverable <i>y</i> from Task <i>x</i>
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Tx.y	Task <i>y</i> from Work package <i>x</i>
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

This deliverable reports the results of Task T8.3 "Dissemination and Users' Engagement Activities". This task, developed in the framework of WP8 "Dissemination and Communication Activities", is concerned, on the one hand, with foreseen and carried out activities developed by BigDataOcean (BDO) partners aiming disseminating its concept and results. The task also envisaged interaction with standardisation bodies, targeting the participation in definition and discussion of standards since the beginning of the project and throughout its duration. The organisation of specific events (as hackathons) has also been considered in the WP8, and this deliverable also reports its status.

On the other hand, the deliverable describes the communication activities that have also been developed and that are foreseen until the end of the project, to promote BigDataOcean and its themes to the media and the public.

The deliverable allows quantifying the achievements and progress facing what has been planned for the first reporting period (M1-M15), while defining new goals on dissemination and communication activities for the second reporting period (M16-M30), based on lessons learned from the former.

1.2 Relation with other Tasks and WPs

This deliverable is strongly related with Task T8.1 "Dissemination, Communication and Maritime Stakeholders Engagement Planning", where, among other, dissemination and communication plans, composed of specific activities and strategies, with targeted key performance indicators (KPIs), were defined. These dissemination and communication plans have been reported in the Deliverable D8.1 "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan, Initial Release" [1]. This deliverable clearly defined dissemination and communication according to European Commission guidelines:

- **Dissemination:** public disclosure of the results of a project across any medium. It is the process of promoting and generating awareness about the project from the very beginning. Its aim is to make the project results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way.
- **Communication:** related to taking measures for promoting the project and its results to a multitude of audiences including the broad public, while engaging in a two-way exchange of information.

These definitions are maintained throughout the present deliverable.

Despite the relation with other project activities, there is a relevant correspondence to Task T2.2 "Maritime Data Stakeholders, Information Sources and Needs Identification", from WP2 "Stakeholders' Identification, Maritime Data Value Chain Definition and Project Methodology". The four workshops that were held to identify stakeholders and envisaged requirements, which constitute a significant dissemination activity, took place in the frame of that task.

1.3 Structure of the Document

Besides this introductory section, this deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the **Dissemination Activities** of BigDataOcean. It starts with a description of envisaged vs. achieved targets for all KPIs relating distinct dissemination mechanisms, as set originally in D8.1. Each of those mechanisms previously defined is individually analysed in the subsections of Section 2. These are the following:
 - Organisation of project events.
 - Participation to conferences and workshops.
 - Scientific publications.
 - Community building/ engagement with stakeholders.
 - Collaboration and synergies with projects.
 - Internal dissemination in partner's networks.
 - Standardisation contributions.

This section ends with a dissemination plan for the second reporting period, where new targets are set for each mechanism, considering achievements of the previous period.

- **Section 3** concerns the **Communication Activities** of the project. The same approach of the preceding section was followed, i.e. starting with the description of communication mechanisms and achievement of goals defined for the first reporting period; and ending with a communication plan for the second reporting period, based on the analysis of the former. The defined communication mechanisms were the following:
 - Project's website.
 - Social media presence.
 - Project's blog.
 - Traditional media and communication material.

2 Dissemination Activities

The first reporting period of BigDataOcean (i.e. M1-M15) expands to the first two phases of the dissemination plan set by the project partners. More specifically, as illustrated also in Figure 1, it covers the Phase I: "Raise Awareness" and the first three months of Phase II: "Inform and Interact". This section reports the activities up to M15 and elaborated a plan for the second half of the project that will complete the execution of Phase II and Phase II: "Promote".

Dissemination Mechanisms	BigDataOcean Phases		
	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M12) Diss. Obj. I, III Activities' Intensity: Low Target Audiences: ALL	Phase II: Inform and Interact (M13-M24) Diss. Obj. I, II, III, IV Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL	Phase III: Promote (M25-M30) Diss. Obj. II, III, IV, V, VI Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL
(D1) Organisation of Project Events	D1.I) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences	D1.II) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences, industry events & fairs; Organisation of hackathon	D1.III) Organisation of workshops in industry events; Organisation of hackathon & demo events
(D2) Participation to Conferences & Workshops	D2.I) Participation to events; Presentation of project scope; Interaction with participants	D2.II) Presentation of project's results to events; Representation in booths	D2.III) Presentation of project's results and business case to events; Representation in demo sessions
(D3) Scientific Publications	D3.I) Publication of position papers / review papers in conferences	D3.II) Publication of methodology papers in conferences	D3.III) Publication of overall project's results in journals & industry magazines
(D4) Community Building / Engagement with Stakeholders	D4.I) Establishment of contact points; Liaison with industry communities and networks; Promotion of project's communication material; Interviews	D4.II) Validation of results with key stakeholders in events / online; Interaction with industry communities and networks; Invitation to project's events	D4.III) Creation of network of potential users; Promotion of project's application stories; Invitation for demos; Training webinars
(D5) Collaboration and synergies with projects	D5.I) Synergies identification; Establishment of contact points; Exchange of ideas & intentions	D5.II) Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, Joint presence in events	D5.III) Joint engagement in events / demo days
(D6) Internal Dissemination in partner's networks	D6.I) Project's links & news in partners' website, social media accounts, newsletters	D6.II) Inclusion of projects' results in partners' events	D6.III) Demonstration of results in partners' premises; Training; Reuse of results
(D7) Standardisation Contributions	D7.I) Registration / participation to relevant working groups; Alignment with existing standards	D7.II) Participation to working groups' telcos and events; Presentation of project's outcomes	D7.III) Participation to working groups' telcos and events; Presentation of project's demos

Figure 1: BigDataOcean Dissemination Plan (from DoA)

2.1 Dissemination results from the first reporting period

As set in Deliverable D8.1, and already mentioned, Dissemination is related with the "public disclosure of the results of a project across any medium. It is the process of promoting and generating awareness about the project from the very beginning. Its aim is to make the project results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way". Taking this into account, several dissemination mechanisms, as well as related KPIs and corresponding targets were defined. The dissemination mechanisms, related KPIs, its originally targets (defined in Section 3 of D8.1) and achieved results, are described in Table 2-1 and Figure 2.

Seven dissemination mechanisms have been defined, each with two or three KPIs, in a total of 19 indicators. From those, 13 have been achieved, although some targets were set to zero (being thus automatically achieved or surpassed). These targets, as mentioned, were established in D8.1. Figure 2 provides a graphical view on the achievement of the KPIs. It is clear that BigDataOcean has been quite active with mechanisms such as D1 "Organisation of project events", D2 "Participation to conferences and workshops", and D5 "Collaboration and synergies with projects", where it has presented excellent indicators overcoming all the milestones initially defined for the period. Regarding distribution, one can

observe in Figure 3 that the preferred dissemination actions have been focused on community building and engagement with the stakeholders, a fundamental activity for the initial stages of the project. A more detailed analysis on these indicators is presented in the following sub-sections.

Table 2-1: Monitoring and evaluation measurements for the first period

Dissemination Mechanism	Related KPIs	Target M15	Achieved M15
D1 "Organisation of project events"	Number of workshops organised	4	9
	Number of hackathons organised	0	1
	Number of demo events	0	0
D2 "Participation to conferences and workshops"	Number of attended events	10	21
	Number of events with project's presentation	7	11
	Number of project's demo booths	0	0
D3 "Scientific publications"	Number of conference papers	5	8
	Number of journal papers	1	0
	Number of articles in industry magazines	4	0
D4 "Community building/ engagement with stakeholders"	Number of industry contact points	50	59
	Number of industry communities informed about the project	5	8
	Number of webinars	1	0
D5 "Collaboration and synergies with projects"	Number of projects with synergies	5	11
	Number of joint activities	4	7
D6 "Internal dissemination in partner's networks"	Number of internal partners' events	5	1
	Number of links to the project's website	15	36
	Number of training sessions	0	0
D7 "Standardisation contributions"	Number of working groups	3	1
	Number of project's presentations in standardisation meeting (online or offline)	3	1

Dissemination KPIs															
Target M15							Achieved M15								
							59								
							36								
21															
9	1	11			8	0	0	8	0	11		7	1	1	1
NUMBER OF WORKSHOPS ORGANISED	NUMBER OF HACKATHONS ORGANISED	NUMBER OF ATTENDED EVENTS	NUMBER OF EVENTS WITH PROJECT'S PRESENTATION	NUMBER OF CONFERENCE PAPERS	NUMBER OF JOURNAL PAPERS	NUMBER OF ARTICLES IN INDUSTRY MAGAZINES	NUMBER OF INDUSTRY CONTACT POINTS	NUMBER OF INDUSTRY COMMUNITIES INFORMED ABOUT THE PROJECT	NUMBER OF WEBINARS	NUMBER OF PROJECTS WITH SYNERGIES	NUMBER OF JOINT ACTIVITIES	NUMBER OF INTERNAL PARTNERS' EVENTS	NUMBER OF LINKS TO THE PROJECT'S WEBSITE	NUMBER OF WORKING GROUPS	NUMBER OF PROJECT'S PRESENTATIONS IN STANDARDISATION MEETING (ONLINE OF OFFLINE)
D1 "ORGANISATION OF PROJECT EVENTS"	D2 "PARTICIPATION TO CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS"	D3 "SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS"			D4 "COMMUNITY BUILDING / ENGAGEMENT WITH STAKEHOLDERS"			D5 "COLLABORATION AND SYNERGIES WITH PROJECTS"	D6 "INTERNAL DISSEMINATION IN PARTNER'S NETWORKS"		D7 "STANDARDISATION CONTRIBUTIONS"				

Figure 2: Achievement of Dissemination KPIs (M15)

Figure 3: Distribution of Dissemination Activities

2.1.1 Organisation of project events

Under this dissemination mechanism, which is related to the internal organisation of events specific to BigDataOcean, all targets have been achieved. Concerning the different KPIs, the following comments are relevant:

- Number of workshops organised: nine workshops have been organised. Among these, four are related with the events associated with definition of requirements for the pilots (in the frame

of T2.2, as already mentioned); three are associated to meetings with specific stakeholders in the context of Pilot 4 "Wave Power as the Next Clean Energy Source"; one is the "CEN Workshop on Big Data", held during the 23rd ICE/ITMC Conference; and the last one corresponds to the Special Session "Big Data Applications & Future Trends", also held during that conference.

- Number of hackathons organised: although no events have been aimed for the first reporting period, one was hosted by BigDataOcean project, with data provided by EXMILE. This hackathon is organised in the framework of the 12th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-Based Systems, DEBS 2018, and is called "DEBS Grand Challenge"¹.

Table I-1, in Annex I, details all the project events reported in this section.

2.1.2 Participation to conferences and workshops

Again, all targets have been achieved in this mechanism, related to participation in events for disseminating BigDataOcean. The target of 10 attended events was more than doubled. Among these, eleven comprised presentation of BigDataOcean project. The events reported in this section are detailed in Table I-2 of Annex I.

2.1.3 Scientific publications

This dissemination mechanism is related to publications detailing results of BigDataOcean as well as related work, in international conferences and journals, besides industry magazines. The targeted number of conference papers has been surpassed, but no journal papers or articles in industry magazines have been published. The reason for this gap is that the focus was given to fast publication channels, considering that only preliminary results were obtained in the first reporting period. Consolidated results will be collected in the second period, as the project evolves, thus allowing to mitigate this gap.

Table I-3 of Annex I details the publications summarised in this section.

2.1.4 Community building/ engagement with stakeholders

This dissemination mechanism aims strengthening the link with end users and stakeholders while building a community around BigDataOcean. It has been one of the main focal points of the BigDataOcean dissemination during the first 15 months. Two of the three targets have been achieved, namely the number of industry contact points and the number of industry communities informed about the project. The third KPI, concerning the number of developed webinars, was not yet achieved and will be done during the last half of the project, with more mature result available for the community. For the sake of effectiveness, it was decided that such dissemination actions will take place when the platform is live. Therefore, the first webinar will take place one month after releasing the platform (M19), being the remaining ones developed shortly after.

¹ <http://www.cs.otago.ac.nz/debs2018/calls/gc.html>

More than 50 contact points with industry, either bilateral contacts or through the events organised, were performed in the first reporting period. From those, it is possible to highlight that the following industry communities have been informed and expressed interest in BigDataOcean:

- Big Data Value Association².
- Research Data Alliance³.
- Oceanology International⁴.
- European Big Data Value Forum⁵.
- Hellenic Institute of Marine Technology⁶.
- 5th Hellenic Forum for Science, Technology and Innovation⁷.
- World Port Hackathon 2017⁸.
- Fórum Oceano⁹.

2.1.5 Collaboration and synergies with projects

This dissemination mechanism was concerned with identifying projects and establishing synergies with BigDataOcean, and among those defining and implementing joint activities. The identified projects, as well as the spokesperson or BigDataOcean partner involved, were:

- *datACRON: Big Data Analytics for Time Critical Mobility Forecasting* (University of Piraeus, Greece)¹⁰.
- *AEGIS: Advanced Big Data Value Chain for Public Safety and Personal Security* (NTUA)¹¹.
- *PredMine: A Predictive Analytics Platform Using Live Big Data* (European Affairs Dept.)¹².
- *AREA: Design, Development & Promotion of an Innovative Business Intelligence Big Data Analytics Platform for Market Research* (European Affairs Dept.).
- *NOBEL GRID: New cost-efficient business models for flexible Smart grids* (UNINOVA)¹³.
- *C2NET: Cloud Collaborative Manufacturing Networks* (UNINOVA)¹⁴.
- *AQUASMART: Aquaculture Smart and Open Data Analytics as a Service* (UNINOVA)¹⁵.
- *OPTIMUM: Multi-source Big Data Fusion Driven Proactivity for Intelligent Mobility* (UNINOVA)¹⁶.
- *ESSNeT Big Data: European Statistical Systems Network* (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, Statistics Netherlands)¹⁷.

² <http://www.bdva.eu/>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴ <http://www.oceanologyinternational.com/>

⁵ <http://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.elint.org.gr/>

⁷ <http://events.demokritos.gr/>

⁸ <https://worldporthackathon.com/>

⁹ <http://www.forumoceano.pt/>

¹⁰ <http://ai-group.ds.unipi.gr/datacron/>

¹¹ <http://www.aegis-bigdata.eu/>

¹² <http://predmine.eu/>

¹³ <http://nobelgrid.eu/>

¹⁴ <http://c2net-project.eu/>

¹⁵ <http://www.aquasmartdata.eu/>

¹⁶ <http://www.optimumproject.eu/>

¹⁷ https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/mwikis/essnetbigdata/index.php/Main_Page

- Marine-EO: *Bridging Innovative Downstream Earth Observation and Copernicus enabled Services for Integrated maritime environment, surveillance and security* (National Centre for Scientific Research, Greece)¹⁸.
- EMODnet: European Marine Observation and Data Network (HCMR)¹⁹.

From these synergies, some joint activities with BigDataOcean and some of the previous projects have been implemented, namely:

- Special Session "Big Data Applications & Future Trends", held during the 23rd ICE/ITM Conference (with OPTIMUM).
- CEN Workshop on Big Data, held also during the 23rd ICE/ITM Conference (with AQUASMART).
- Participation in the following Workshops (with dataCRON):
 - MATES 2017 – Mobility Analytics for Spatio-temporal and Social Data²⁰.
 - BMDA 2018 – Big Mobility Data Analytics²¹.
 - Maritime Big Data Workshop²².
- Attendance of the ESSNeT Big Data plenary meeting.
- Presenting activities of BigDataOcean during the Open Sea Lab Hackathon (with EMODnet)²³.

All the targets in this dissemination mechanism have been achieved.

2.1.6 Internal dissemination in partner's networks

This dissemination mechanism is related to the internal communication of project results, knowledge exchange and increased awareness about BigDataOcean. Two of the three envisaged targets have been achieved, namely the number of links to the project website and the number of training sessions (although no specific sessions have been envisaged for this period). The third target, concerning the number of internal partners' events, was below expectations and therefore an increased effort will be carried out from M15 to M30 to achieve the expected results.

On November 2017, EXMILE organised an event celebrating MarineTraffic 10 years of operation. Several stakeholders including ship owners, ship suppliers, port authorities and researchers, among other, have been invited to attend the event, during which the company's research team presented the activities of BigDataOcean project.

Also, several links have been established for the project's website, such as:

- <http://www.bdva.eu/?q=node/658>
- <https://2017.eswc-conferences.org/program/eu-project-networking-session>
- https://www.ren.pt/pt-PT/sustentabilidade_old/a_idi_na_ren/?culture=pt-PT

¹⁸ <https://marine-eo.eu/>

¹⁹ <http://www.emodnet.eu/>

²⁰ <http://ai-group.ds.unipi.gr/mates17/>

²¹ <http://www.datastories.org/bmda18/>

²² <http://www.cmre.nato.int/maritime-big-data-workshop-home>

²³ <http://www.opensealab.eu/>

2.1.7 Standardisation contributions

This dissemination mechanism concerns the opportunity of aligning BigDataOcean activities with standardisation bodies from the beginning of the project, aiming to observe, discuss and even influence emerging standards. A working group has been established in CEN to address standardisation in big data "CEN Workshop on Big Data"²⁴ to which BigDataOcean is now a part of, having organised a meeting during the 23rd ICE/ITM Conference. BigDataOcean was presented and committed to cooperate in the WS Big Data.

2.2 Dissemination plan for the second reporting period

Considering the achievements of the first reporting period, the targets and KPIs associated with the seven dissemination mechanisms were revisited considering the final part of the project and the impact such dissemination actions can produce. These new targets (corresponding only to the M16-M30 period) are described in Table 2-2. To note that some of the overall project indicators have already been accomplished (e.g. Number of workshops organised). However, such activities are important to potentiate the project results hence the expected metric values have been extended.

Table 2-2: Monitoring and evaluation measurements for the second period

Dissemination Mechanism	Related KPIs	Target M16-M30
D1 "Organisation of project events"	Number of workshops organised	4
	Number of hackathons organised	1
	Number of demo events	4
D2 "Participation to conferences and workshops"	Number of attended events	9
	Number of events with project's presentation	9
	Number of project's demo booths	2
D3 "Scientific publications"	Number of conference papers	7
	Number of journal papers	4
	Number of articles in industry magazines	8
D4 "Community building/ engagement with stakeholders"	Number of industry contact points	59
	Number of industry communities informed about the project	5
	Number of webinars	4
D5 "Collaboration and synergies with projects"	Number of projects with synergies	4
	Number of joint activities	3
D6 "Internal dissemination in partner's networks"	Number of internal partners' events	9
	Number of links to the project's website	14
	Number of training sessions	4
D7 "Standardisation contributions"	Number of working groups	2
	Number of project's presentations in standardisation meeting (online or offline)	5

²⁴ <https://www.cen.eu/News/Workshops/Pages/WS-2016-14.aspx>

Some of the planned dissemination activities envisaged for the second reporting period are described in Table 2-3. These include attending conferences, workshops and forums, as well as publications in selected journals, which include includes: Big Data Research, Journal of Big Data, International Journal of Big Data Intelligence, Big Data and Information Analytics, Journal of Maritime Research, Journal of Ocean Technologies, Computers and Geosciences, Computers in Industry, amongst others.

Table 2-3: Planned dissemination events to attend on the second reporting period

Name	Date	Location	Type	Target Audience	Involved Partners
WWW2018 World Wide Web (The Web Conference)	Apr, 2018	Lyon, France	Conference	Researchers and Academia	UBONN
ESWC 2018 - The 18th Extended Semantic Web Conference	Jun, 2018	Crete, Greece	Conference	Researchers and Academia	UBONN
SEMANTiCS 2018	Sept, 2018	Vienna, Austria	Conference	Researchers and Academia	UBONN
ESWC 2019 - The 19th Extended Semantic Web Conference	Jun, 2019	TBA	Conference	Researchers and Academia	UBONN
IEEE Intelligent Systems 2018	September, 2018	Madeira, Portugal	Conference	Researchers and Academia	UNINOVA, NESTER, ...
PICASSO	May, 2018	Gijon, Spain	Workshop	Researchers, Academia, Industry	ANEK
EAST MEDITERRANEAN SUPERYACHT FORUM	June, 2018	Athens, Greece	Forum	Industry	ANEK, FOINIKAS
FIBRESHIP	June, 2018	Cambridge, UK	Workshop	Researchers, Academia, Industry	ANEK, FOINIKAS
BDVA	(every 2-3 months)	Brussels, Belgium	Forum	Industry	EXMILE, NTUA, ISMB
Forum do mar/ Business2sea 2018	November 2018	Porto, Portugal	Forum	Industry, Researchers, Academia	NESTER, UNINOVA
Maritime Big Data Workshop	May, 2018	La Spezia, Italy	Workshop	Researchers, Academia, Industry	EXMILE
European Big Data Value Forum	November, 2018	Vienna, Austria	Forum	Researchers, Academia, Industry	EXMILE, NTUA
IEEE BigData 2018	December 2018	Seattle, USA	Conference	Research, Academia, Industry	EXMILE

3 Communication Activities

The first reporting period of BigDataOcean project (i.e. M1-M15) expands to the first two phases of the communication plan set by the project partners. More specifically, as illustrated also in Figure 4, it covers the Phase I: "Raise Awareness" and the first three months of Phase II: "Diffuse Knowledge".

Communication Mechanisms	BigDataOcean Phases		
	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M12) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	Phase II: Diffuse Knowledge (M13-M24) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	Phase III: Communication Culmination (M25-M30) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, IV, V, VI</i>
(C1) Project's Website	C1.I) Design & Development of an intuitive and responsive project's web site; Search engine optimization	C1.II) Regular update of the website content; Watch website's analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest	C1.III) Regular update of the website content; Clear visibility of results, demo / application material in an interactive way
(C2) Social Media Presence	C2.I) Establishment of presence in: Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags; Upload public material; Follow influencers of the domain; Engage with other projects and initiatives	C2.II) Promote project's outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags	C2.III) Promote project's outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content (more sporadically)
(C3) Project's Blog	C3.I) Deploy project's blog; Provide blog posts related to project's positioning & technologies	C3.II) Provide frequent blog posts to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback	C3.III) Publish frequent blog posts to demonstrate and promote project's results
(C4) Traditional Media	C4.I) Press release to announce the project's launch	C4.II) Press releases to announce the significant events / results	C4.III) Press releases to promote the business case of the project's results
(C5) Communication Material	C5.I) Design logo and project identity; Prepare project factsheet, brochure, banner, e-Newsletter and promo video	C5.II) Prepare revised brochure, banner and frequent releases of e-Newsletter; Publish blogs / news in EU instruments (e.g. Cordis News, research*eu magazines etc.)	C5.III) Prepare final brochure, banner, frequent releases of e-Newsletter and video demonstrators; Publish blogs / news in EU dissemination instruments

Figure 4: BigDataOcean Communication strategy

For each phase, the BigDataOcean communication strategy is implemented through a set of communication mechanisms aiming to meet the corresponding communication objectives for that phase. The communication objectives of BigDataOcean are the following:

- I. Create awareness of the project among the full range of potential adopters/ users in the general public.
- II. Provide a clear view of the project's concept, goals and results by formulating adapted key messages, and preparing communication material.
- III. Create an active community of potential users and collect feedback to be taken into account by the project's activities.
- IV. Prepare the ground for the exploitation of project's results.
- V. Support targeted dissemination of the project's results.
- VI. Foster the wide adoption of the project's results in industry and society.

In the following subsections the results of the communication activities during the first period are reported, and the plan for the second period of the project is described.

3.1 Communication results from the first reporting period

The communication results of the project are broken down to the project's communication mechanisms described in each of the following subsections, together with the actions taken by the project partners.

Table 3-1 lists all the communication measurements determined for the first period, the success criterion and the actual status. It can be verified that BigDataOcean has shown an exceptional track to date for most of the measured activities and will be substantially increasing communication activities throughout the rest of the project now that the live demo and prototypes are available for public presentations and demonstrations.

Table 3-1: Monitoring and evaluation measurements for the first period

Communication Mechanisms	Related KPIs	Target M15	Achieved M15
C1 "Project's Website"	Number of unique visitors	2000	2707
	Average duration of visits (min)	2	2:14
	Number of page views	5000	10215
C2 "Social media presence"	Number of accumulative followers in social media	375	176
	Number of accumulative posts	500	58
	Number of interactions in social media	125	292
C3 "Project's blog"	Number of posts in website	25	20
	Number of interactions	50	91
C4 "Traditional media"	Number of press releases	4	0
C5 "Communication material"	Number of project's factsheets/ brochures and banners	5	5
	Number of e-Newsletters	5	0
	Number of videos	1	1
	Number of blog posts in EC mechanisms	3	6

3.1.1 Project's website

The project's website has been set up and running since the first month of the project. There BigDataOcean partners have listed general information about the project in home page, and in the about page, as well as updates related to the project's findings and the events where BigDataOcean partners participated (i.e. listed in news and events pages). Finally, the website offers to its visitors the capability to receive news relevant to the project and its piloting activities by registering to the project's newsletter. Through the participation and the organisation of workshops and conferences BigDataOcean partners promoted the project activities and redirected interested stakeholders to the project's website. These actions resulted in increasing website's visibility and the next figures, produced through Google Analytics, show that BigDataOcean website has a global reach (see Figure 5) with more

than 2500 unique visitors (see Figure 6), accessing ~10k pages in total (see Figure 7) with average session duration more than 2 minutes (see Figure 8).

Figure 5: Session distribution per country

Figure 6: Visitors' distribution over time and total number of users

Figure 7: Page views distribution over time and total number of page views

Figure 8: Sessions' distribution over time, total # of sessions and average duration

3.1.2 Social media presence

From its beginning, BigDataOcean has established a set of social media accounts to boost the visibility of the project and to maximise the communication means with the user communities that are relevant to the project’s scope and its achievements.

Figure 9 shows the running sums of daily total reach, engaged users and new likes. The results show a continuous increase. In addition, a rapid increase has been observed in October 2017, when BigDataOcean announced the acceptance of a scientific paper in IEEE Big Data, one of the most prestigious conferences in the area. Similar trends are also observed in statistics extracted from the BigDataOcean twitter account. Figure 10 highlights the running sums of tweets, likes and impressions capturing the reachability of BigDataOcean Twitter account to its followers.

Figure 9: BigDataOcean Facebook page statistics

Figure 10: BigDataOcean Twitter account statistics

3.1.3 Project's blog

BigDataOcean website also includes two sections where news and events of the project are posted. Table 3-2 lists all the blog posts produced during the first period of the project.

Table 3-2: Blog posts of the first reporting period

Blog post title	Type	Date published
BigDataOcean's fourth plenary meeting in Athens	Events	12-03-18
BigDataOcean at European Big Data Value Forum	News	01-12-17
BigDataOcean's 3rd plenary meeting at Chania	Events	24-10-17
BigDataOcean attended the Copernicus Marine Week	News	17-10-17
BigDataOcean and ESSnet Big Data project join forces	News	05-10-17
BigDataOcean was presented at MATES 2017	News	15-09-17
BigDataOcean project presented during "Challenges to exploit Big Maritime Data" workshop	News	10-07-17
BigDataOcean's second plenary meeting at Madeira	Events	07-07-17
BigDataOcean was presented at ESWC 2017	News	09-06-17
Big Data Value Association Activity Group meeting	News	20-03-17
Workshop on wave power	Events	17-03-17
Workshop on fault prediction and proactive maintenance	Events	14-03-17

Blog post title	Type	Date published
Workshop on mare protection	Events	10-03-17
Workshop on maritime security and anomaly detection	Events	03-03-17
Running a Prototyping Sprint with BigDataOcean	News	21-02-17
BigDataOcean at the "Information and Networking Days Big Data PPP" event in Luxembourg	Events	27-01-17
Kick-off meeting overview.	Events	27-01-17
BigDataOcean kick-off meeting	Events	30-12-16
The BigDataOcean project	News	28-12-16

3.1.4 Traditional media and Communication Material

During the first period of the project, BigDataOcean partners have put significant effort to produce high quality brochures. The first brochure, in the form of a 4-page leaflet, was delivered early in the project (M5) including information relevant to the project's objective, its target users, the consortium, etc., as depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: BigDataOcean leaflet

Then, as the project evolved, partners aimed to promote pilot activities and thus four two-pages flyers have been designed and produced. The front page of each flyer is common for all the pilots including general information about the project. The back page of each flyer is dedicated to the corresponding pilot, including the pilot's goal, description and contact points. The content of the flyers is depicted in Figure 12. Furthermore, BigDataOcean partners have prepared two posters during the first year of the project, see Figure 13, which have been used in conferences and booths to increase project's networking and promote project's activities.

Finally, the project has produced a video, used to promote the BigDataOcean platform to related stakeholders. The video is available at the project repository²⁵.

²⁵ <https://alfresco.epu.ntua.gr/share/page/site/bigdataocean/document-details?nodeRef=workspace://SpacesStore/620a80d1-41d1-40bc-afcd-a02c788519f4>

BigDataOcean
Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications

Pilot 1: Fault Prediction and Proactive Maintenance
 GOAL: Damage and mechanical failures prediction and proactive maintenance of vessel equipment.
 DESCRIPTION: Nowadays, naval engineers and shipping companies try to constantly minimise fixed and operational costs, as well as their impact on the maritime and generic environment. Amongst the main reasons that need to be significantly reduced are unexpected damage and/or mechanical failures. Providing a simple overview of the effect of such phenomena one can report high costs of repairs and spare parts (especially when requested in as close to real-time as possible), loss of earnings due to immobilisation of vessels and/or due to failure to comply with Service Level Agreements (SLAs) or even port state control (PSC) detentions.
 Through this pilot, data from every available source will be collected and formulated a knowledge base that each owner and/or operator exploits towards the effort of being proactive rather than reactive. These data, after being cleaned and integrated, will enable data analytics for ship management including maintenance recommendations.

Pilot 2: Mare protection from oil spills
 GOAL: Improve the forecasting skill of Posidon Oil Spill Service for effective response against hazardous oil spill accidents at sea and contingency planning.
 DESCRIPTION: Oil spill models provide an essential asset in contingency planning and in preparing effective response strategies against hazardous oil spills at sea. Such models rely on the ability to predict meteo-marine conditions of the sea by using cross-sectional data, including outputs from atmospheric, wave and hydrological numerical models. The derived forecasted fields will combine information on the location, rate, nature and characteristics of an oil spill and provide, in advance, some knowledge on the fate and track of the oil dispersion through time. An integrated Big data infrastructure providing targeted services and additional datasets of interest, could increase the forecasting skill and improve the effectiveness of the operational activities and thus, have a significant impact on marine and environment protection.
 This pilot will provide oil spill forecast services for the marine environment and the test case will take place in the Aegean Sea. Forecasting simulations, enhanced with various cross-sectional marine data, will take advantage of the extended ocean data volume and variability.

Pilot 3: Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection
 GOAL: Identify vessel routes based on their motion patterns to act proactively and minimise threats at sea.
 DESCRIPTION: Events, activities and threats in the maritime ecosystem could potentially impact global safety, economic activity or the environment. Understanding of such events, activities, and threats, known as Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA), has been ineffective in the past due to the lack of data. However, current tracking technologies have transformed the problem into one of an overwhelming amount of information, leading to a need for automated analysis. The major challenge to be addressed in this pilot is developing the ability to identify patterns within vast amounts of data, fused from various sources, so as to act proactively and minimise the impact of possible threats. Anomaly detection can be defined as a method that supports situation assessment process by indicating objects and situations that, in some sense, deviate from the expected, known or "normal" behaviour and thus may be of interest for further investigation.
 This pilot will perform behaviour and pattern analysis of enhanced trajectories/vessel profiles, enabling vessel movement information (e.g. courses of turns, turn around, tails, speed etc. in a given time window, etc.) and assess the risks to accurately predict maritime security or movement anomaly incidents.

Pilot 4: Wave power as the next clean energy source
 GOAL: Predict best locations, impact on equipment operation and on environment for wave energy production.
 DESCRIPTION: This pilot aims to improve the characterisation of the ocean as a resource for energy, particularly considering wave energy conversion. This industry is still in its infancy with different technological challenges representing key barriers to its further development. Among others, it depends on the availability of large datasets and physical testing facilities to continue its development. Due to the large costs involved, simulation of converters and the accurate choice of pilot locations are extremely important. This pilot will consider data from a pilot zone in the west coast of Portugal and, through the outputs of the pilot, improve the characterisation of this zone and potentiate other pilot zones in Europe.
 Five main phases reflect the process followed in this pilot: modelling, measurement and acquisition, data curation, assessment and installation planning. The pilot success will be evaluated throughout a series of well-established KPIs that evaluate the technical feasibility of the wave energy plant but also its impact in the environment.

Figure 12: BigDataOcean Pilot flyers

BigDataOcean
Exploiting oceans of data for maritime applications

Objectives
 BigDataOcean aims to provide a multi-segment platform that combines data of different velocity, variety and volume, using an inter-linked, trusted, multi-pool engine.
 BigDataOcean will build a big data repository to deliver high quality value-added services to a large number of stakeholders.

Pilots
 1. Vessel Fault Prediction and Proactive Maintenance
 2. Mare Protection
 3. Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection
 4. Wave Power

Stakeholders
 BigDataOcean is targeted towards all possible stakeholders involved in maritime applications. Ship builders, ship owners and operators, freight forwarders and logistics companies, big operators, charterers and cargo companies, public authorities and NGOs are some examples of stakeholders that will benefit from the BigDataOcean services.

Big Maritime Data Architecture
 Public authorities, Entrepreneurs, Maritime operators, NGOs, Local communities, Scientists, Energy companies.
 Applications: Query Processing, Data Analytics, Data Visualisation, Semantic enrichment, Data Curation, Data Integration.
 Open data, IoT data, Secondary data, Scientific data, Social data, Historical data, Biological data.

Stakeholders and User Communities
 BigDataOcean is targeted towards all possible stakeholders involved in maritime applications. Ship builders, ship owners and operators, freight forwarders and logistics companies, big operators, charterers and cargo companies, public authorities and NGOs are some examples of stakeholders that will benefit from the BigDataOcean services.

Figure 13: BigDataOcean posters

3.2 Communication plan for the second reporting period

To set up the plan for the second reporting period the communication success criteria for the first period is first revisited and then compared against the actual values. Table 3-3 details the monitoring and evaluation measurements for the second period of the project. It should be noted that the success criterion column includes the one set for the second period only, and additional actions will be implemented, if not during the first period.

Finally, Table 3-4 indicates the way BigDataOcean partners will be active in communicating project's achievements through the blog and social media accounts of the project.

One of the conclusions of the first reporting period is the relevance of a dynamic presence in the social media. This requires a dedicated coordinator that can manage and promote communication, assuring that this flows in a timely manner. Therefore, one BigDataOcean team member, namely Dimitris Zissis from EXMILE, is appointed as coordinator for the BigDataOcean presence in social media.

Table 3-3: Monitoring and evaluation measurements for the second period

Dissemination Mechanism	Measurement Type	Success criteria (M16-M30)
C1 "Project's Website"	Number of unique visitors	3000
	Average duration of visits (min)	2
	Number of page views	5000
C2 "Social media presence"	Number of accumulative followers in social media	574
	Number of accumulative posts	942
	Number of interactions in social media	125
C3 "Project's blog"	Number of posts in website	30
	Number of interactions	50
C4 "Traditional media"	Number of press releases	8
C5 "Communication material"	Number of project's factsheets/ brochures and banners	5
	Number of e-Newsletters	7
	Number of videos	1
	Number of blog posts in EC mechanisms	3

Table 3-4: Blog and social media posting strategy

Partner	Post theme	Indicative Date
ANEK	Review meeting in Luxembourg	M17
FOINIKAS	Review meeting in Luxembourg	M17
UBONN	BDO at the Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC) 2018	M17
ANEK	Participation in POSEIDONIA and reference to the project	M18
EXMILE	Result of project's interim review	M18

Partner	Post theme	Indicative Date
HCMR	Mare Protection Pilot Initial Results & Midterm Review Results	M18
FOINIKAS	Participation in POSEIDONIA and reference to the project	M18
UBITECH	Vessel Fault Prediction Pilot Evaluation - Initial Results	M18
UNINOVA	Announcement of IEEE IS 2018 in Madeira and the associated BDO events	M18
EXMILE	DEBS 2018 challenge results	M19
ANEK	Report on the project's progress in ANEK's website	M19
FOINIKAS	Report on the project's progress in AVIN's Internationals site	M19
UBONN	BDO Metadata Repository and its evaluation	M20
EXMILE	Workshop organisation	M20
NESTER	Participation in SEST2018 conference (if attended)	M21
NTUA	CeDem/ eGov conference (if attended)	M21
NTUA	BDVA Events/ Big Data PPP (tentative)	M22
UNINOVA	Report of IEEE IS 2018 in Madeira and the associated BDO events	M22
EXMILE	European Big Data Value Forum participation	M23
UBONN	Harmonisation of Big Data Ocean data	M23
NESTER	Participation in Business2sea 2018	M23
UBITECH	BDO Platform major release	M24
EXMILE	Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection pilot services	M25
ISMB	Blog post on the application of "Journey from Lab to Market" to BDO	M25
ANEK	Project progress update	M25
FOINIKAS	Project progress update	M25
UBONN	Evaluation of BDO Harmonisation tool	M26
NESTER	Pilot services description and status	M27
ANEK	Report on BDO platform initial evaluation results	M27
FOINIKAS	Report on BDO platform initial evaluation results	M27
ANEK	Post for the completion of the project in ANEK website	M30
EXMILE	Result of project review	M30
FOINIKAS	Post for the completion of the project in AVIN's Internationals site	M30
ISMB	Blog posts on BDO results and market perspectives (post 1)	M30
ISMB	Blog posts on BDO results and market perspectives (post 2)	M30
ISMB	Blog posts on BDO results and market perspectives (post 3)	M30
UBITECH	Vessel Fault Prediction Pilot Evaluation - Final Results	M30
HCMR	Mare Protection Pilot Final Results	M30
UNINOVA	Final results and project overview	M30

4 Conclusion and Next Steps

This document presents an overview and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities and approaches of BigDataOcean first reporting period (M1-M15), whose analysis allows adjusting or defining new targets, or taking correcting actions concerning this major pillar of BigDataOcean for the second reporting period (M16-M30). Both activities had several targets that surpassed expectations, while other must be improved.

Concerning **Dissemination Activities**, deviations have been identified and mitigating measures are envisaged. This is the case of e.g. publication in scientific journals, which is expected to be accomplished in the second reporting period, as results start to be consolidated. In the first period, only preliminary results were available, and the natural focus was to target fast dissemination channels, as the publication in technical-scientific conferences, which more than doubled initial targets. Other future steps include organising hackathons, providing webinars, organising training sessions or make presentations in standardisation meetings.

In what concerns **Communications Activities**, the major conclusion is the opportunity of having a dynamic, timely presence in social media (including social networks and blog). That requires a coordinator that can manage such communications, ensuring the flow of information (internally and externally), for which a team member, Dimitris Zissis from EXMILE, is appointed for that role.

A global view of dissemination and communication KPIs, as well as targets during and at the end of the second reporting period, is shown in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Target results for the dissemination mechanisms during and at the end of the second reporting period.

Dissemination Mechanism	Related KPIs	Target 2nd period	Target M30 accum.
D1 "Organisation of project events"	Number of workshops organised	4	13
	Number of hackathons organised	1	2
	Number of demo events	4	4
D2 "Participation to conferences and workshops"	Number of attended events	9	30
	Number of events with project's presentation	9	20
	Number of project's demo booths	2	2
D3 "Scientific publications"	Number of conference papers	7	15
	Number of journal papers	4	4
	Number of articles in industry magazines	8	8
D4 "Community building/ engagement with stakeholders"	Number of industry contact points	50	109
	Number of industry communities informed about the project	5	13
	Number of webinars	4	4
D5 "Collaboration and synergies with projects"	Number of projects with synergies	4	15
	Number of joint activities	3	10
D6 "Internal dissemination in partner's networks"	Number of internal partners' events	9	10
	Number of links to the project's website	14	50
	Number of training sessions	4	4
D7 "Standardisation contributions"	Number of working groups	2	3
	Number of project's presentations in standardisation meeting (online of offline)	5	6
C1 "Project's Website"	Number of unique visitors	3000	5707
	Average duration of visits (min)	2	2
	Number of page views	5000	15215
C2 "Social media presence"	Number of accumulative followers in social media	574	750
	Number of accumulative posts	942	1 000
	Number of interactions in social media	125	417
C3 "Project's blog"	Number of posts in website	30	50
	Number of interactions	50	141
C4 "Traditional media"	Number of press releases	8	8
C5 "Communication material"	Number of project's factsheets/ brochures and banners	5	10
	Number of e-Newsletters	7	7
	Number of videos	1	2
	Number of blog posts in EC mechanisms	3	9

References

- [1] BigDataOcean deliverable "D8.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Plan, Initial Release", http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/BigDataOcean_Dissemination_Communication_and_Stakeholder_Engagement_Plan_Initial_Release-v1.00.pdf

Annex I: Breakdown of Dissemination Results

Table I-1: Results from dissemination mechanism D1 "Organisation of project events"

Type	Title	Date	Location	Persons involved	Short description	Website	Audience	Benefits for BDO	Impact of the dissemination on Action
Workshop	"Mare Protection Pilot" Requirements Workshop	March 2 nd , 2017	Athens, Greece	HCMR: Antonis Chalkiopoulos, Evi Bourma, Maria Sotiropoulou NTUA: Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Spiros Mouzakitis, Papaspyros	Discussion of the pilot technical and data requirements	n/a			
Workshop	"Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection Pilot" Requirements Workshop	February 23 rd , 2017	Athens, Greece	EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis, Dimitris Zisis, Argyris Stasinakis NTUA: Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Spyros Mouzakitis, Askounis	Presentation of the pilot to stakeholders and data providing agreement	n/a	Pilot stakeholder, data providers and end/ users	Presentatio n of project and pilot to possible stakeholder s/ end-users and assure additional sources of data	Number of participants: 5 from different stakeholders
Workshop	"Vessel Fault Protection Pilot" Requirements Workshop		Athens, Greece	NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Dimitris Papaspyros ANEK: Marinos Nomikos, Panagiotis Vasileiou, Michalis Pachnos FOINIKAS: Stylianos Dafermos, Michalis Androulakakis, Sotiris Anagnostopoulos, Fani Panagopoulou	Discussion of the pilot's technical and data requirement and its business value	n/a			

Workshop	"Wave Power Pilot" Stakeholder / Data Providers meeting	February 8 th , 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	NESTER: Francisco Reis, Nuno Amaro	Presentation of the pilot to stakeholders and data providing agreement	n/a	Pilot stakeholder, data providers and end-users	Presentatio n of project and pilot to possible stakeholder s/ end-users and assure additional sources of data	Number of participants: 5 (from different stakeholders: ENONDAS and Maretec + NESTER)
Workshop	"Wave Power Pilot" Stakeholder/ Data Providers meeting	February 21 st , 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	NESTER: Francisco Reis, Nuno Amaro	Updated presentation of the pilot to stakeholders	n/a	Pilot stakeholder, data providers and end-users	Ensure stakeholder s and end-users for implemente d services	Number of participants: 7 (from different stakeholders: WavEC, ENONDAS and Fórum Oceano + NESTER)
Workshop	"Wave Power Pilot" Requirements Workshop	March 2 nd , 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	NESTER: Nuno Amaro UNINOVA: Carlos Agostinho, João Murta Pina, José Ferreira and Rui Amaral Lopes	Presentation of pilot to stakeholders, user-stories and requirements collection	n/a	Pilot stakeholders, data providers and end-users	Presentatio n of project and pilot to possible stakeholder s/ end-users	Number of participants: 10 (from different stakeholders: ENONDAS, Instituto Hidrográfico and WavEC + Nester and UNINOVA)
Workshop	"Wave Power Pilot" Stakeholder meeting	November 9th, 2017	Lisbon, Portugal	NESTER: Nuno Amaro, Francisco Reis and Rui Alves UNINOVA: João Murta Pina, José Ferreira and Rui Amaral Lopes	Update of pilot services to ensure stakeholder engagement	n/a	Pilot stakeholders, data providers and end-users	update stakeholder s on pilot services and reassure their involvement	Number of participants: 7 (from different stakeholders: WavEC and ENONDAS + Nester and UNINOVA)
Standardisation Workshop	CEN Workshop on Big Data	27 June 2017	Madeira Island, Portugal	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis	Workshop/ participation to working groups	http://dev.ice-conference.org/	Industry and Research	Know-how on the latest developmen	Number of participants: 30

				ISMB: Enrico Ferro, Matteo Ferraris NTUA: Spyros Mouzakis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou UNINOVA (organiser): Carlos Agostinho				ts on standardisation on big data	
Special Session	Big Data Applications & Future Trends	28 June 2017	Madeira Island, Portugal	NESTER: Nuno Amaro UNINOVA: Carlos Agostinho, João Murta Pina and José Ferreira NTUA: Spyros Mouzakis and Panagiotis Kokkinakos EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis	This special session envisaged to bring together R&D developments on Big Data domain, exploiting use cases in various sectors going beyond the specific IT developments on Big Data technology.	http://dev.ice-conference.org/	Industry and Academia	Awareness raising, liaisons with other projects and initiatives and publication of project's preliminary results	Number of participants: 20
Hackathon	ACM DEBS 2018 Grand Challenge	June 25-29, 2018	Hamilton, New Zealand	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis	Contestants will use machine learning to make maritime transportation more reliable. They should explore multiple gigabytes of real maritime spatio-temporal streaming data and compete with peers from academia and industry for the Grand Challenge prize.	http://www.cs.otago.ac.nz/debs2018/calls/gc.html	Academia	Project promotion, Boost visibility	Number of participants: not available yet

Table I-2: Results from dissemination mechanism D2 “Participation to conferences and workshops”

Type	Title	Date	Location	Persons involved	Short description	Website	Audience	Benefits for BigDataOcean	Impact of the dissemination action
Info Day	Big Data PPP Information and Networking Days 2017	17-18 January 2017	Luxembourg	NTUA Dimitris Askounis	Project presentation	http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/document.cfm?doc_id=42183	Researchers, Academia, H2020 Stakeholders	Awareness raising	Number of participants: 25
Workshop	SONNETS Workshop	10 February 2017	Athens, Greece	NTUA: Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Spyros Mouzakitis	Innovating the public sector with emerging ICTs – development of research directions	http://www.sonnets-project.eu/content/sonnets-wp3-workshop-presentations-available-0	Policy makers, Researchers, Academia, Citizens, H2020 stakeholders	Awareness raising, liaisons with other projects and initiatives’ and synergies’ investigation	Number of participants: 30
Workshop	CloudTeams Workshop	16 February 2017	Athens, Greece	NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Dimitrios Papaspyros	Product Management in Software Engineering: from Theory to Practice	https://about.cloudteams.eu/news/cloudteams-workshop-in-athens/	Developers, SMEs, Industry and H2020 stakeholders	Learning on trends in software engineering, investigation of synergies, and awareness raising	Number of participants: 30
Workshop	Big Data PPP Steering Committee 1	13 March 2017	Brussels, Belgium	NTUA Dimitris Askounis	Project presentation	n/a	Big Data PPP stakeholders	Synergies with other Big Data PPP projects, knowledge exchange, and awareness raising	Number of participants: 25
Other	Big Data Value Association Activity Group Meeting	14-15 March 2017	Brussels, Belgium	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis, Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis	Project presentation	n/a	Research and Industry	Ensure maximum visibility of the project, establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for	Number of participants: 30

								knowledge transfer	
Workshop	INNOVATHENS Synergy Workshop	18 May 2017	Athens, Greece	NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Giannis Tsapelas	Project presentation	n/a	INNOVATHENS representatives	Synergy investigation and awareness raising	Number of participants: 10
Workshop	Pilot Blue Cloud Workshop	13 June 2017	Brussels, Belgium	NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis	Project presentation	n/a	Maritime environment stakeholders and H2020 stakeholders	Knowledge exchange, awareness raising and synergies' investigation	Number of participants: 30
Workshop	E-Sides Synergy Workshop	25 June 2017	Madeira, Portugal	NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou	Participation		H2020 stakeholders	Synergy investigation and awareness raising	Number of participants: 30
Standardisation Workshop	CEN Workshop on Big Data	27 June 2017	Madeira Island, Portugal	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis ISMB: Enrico Ferro, Matteo Ferraris NTUA: Spyros Mouzakitis, Panagiotis Kokkinakos, Ariadni Michalitsi-Psarrou UNINOVA (organiser): Carlos Agostinho	Workshop/participation to working groups	http://dev.ice-conference.org/	Industry and Research	Know-how on the latest developments on standardisation on big data	Number of participants: 30

Conference	23rd ICE/ITM Conference	27-29 June 2017	Madeira Island, Portugal	NESTER: Nuno Amaro UNINOVA: Carlos Agostinho, João Murta Pina and José Ferreira NTUA: Spyros Mouzakis and Panagiotis Kokkinakos EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis	Presentation of several scientific papers	http://dev.ice-conference.org/	Academia and Research	Publication of project's results	Number of participants: ~400
Workshop	Mobility Analytics for Spatio-temporal and Social Data (MATES2017)	28 August – 01 September 2017	Munich, Germany	EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis, Dimitris Zissis, Giannis Spiliopoulos	Presentation of a scientific paper	http://ai-group.ds.unipi.gr/mates17/MATES17.html	Academia and Research	Publication of project's results	Number of participants: 30
Conference	Copernicus Marine Week	25-29 September 2017	Brussels, Belgium	HCMR: Antonis Chalkiopoulos, Leonidas Perivoliotis	Poster presentation of different data integration methods of Copernicus products	http://www.copernicusmarineweek.eu	Institutions, agencies, regional stakeholders, entrepreneurs, service providers and scientists	Increase awareness and promote collaborations	Number of Participants: 500-600
Conference/meeting with other projects and project proposers	ICT Proposers' Day	09-10 October 2017	Budapest, Hungary	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis ISMB: Giuseppe Rizzo NTUA:	Participation	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/events/ict-proposers-day-2017	Researchers, academia, industry, SMEs, entrepreneurs and	Establish liaisons with other projects, initiatives for knowledge transfer and	Number of participants: 800

				Dimitris Askounis			H2020 stakeholders	awareness raising	
External community Hackathon	Open Sea Lab - 1st EMODnet Hackathon	15 November 2017	Antwerp, Belgium	HCMR: Maria Sotiropoulou	Project and pilots presentation	http://www.opensealab.eu http://www.emodnet.eu/open-sea-lab-0 http://www.emodnet.eu/open-sea-lab-teams-demonstrate-innovative-uses-marine-data	Marine industry and software developers	Increase awareness and promote collaborations	Number of Participants: 70
Conference	European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF17)	21-23 November 2017	Versailles, France	EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis ISMB: Michele Osella NTUA: Dimitris Askounis, Spyros Mouzakitis HCMR: Antonis Chalkiopoulos, Leonidas Perivoliotis and Maria Sotiropoulou	Project's Booth/ Pilots presentation	http://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/	R&D managers, industry executives, policy makers and researchers	Ensure maximum visibility of the project, establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge transfer and attract potential users and clients	Number of participants: 1000 Number of flyers: 500
Conference	IEEE Big Data	11-14 December 2017	Boston, USA	EXMILE: Dimitris Zissis	Presentation of a scientific paper	http://cci.drexel.edu/bigdata/bigdata2017/index.html	Academia/ and Industry	Publication of project's results	Number of participants: 1000
Conference	2017 Annual Meeting of Marine Technology	12-13 December 2017	Athens, Greece	EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolakis	Project/ Pilots presentation, Booth	http://www.elintconference.gr/	Technology Providers, Shipping Companies, Academia (i.e., Researchers, Professors etc.)	Ensure maximum visibility of the project, attract potential users/ clients	Number of participants: 200 (research and maritime industry)

Workshop	RDA EU Data Innovation Forum	30 January 2018	Brussels, Belgium	EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolak is	Participation / Project's presentation	https://www.rd-alliance.org/ rdae-data-innov-forum-2018	Academia and Research	Ensure maximum visibility of the project, establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge transfer	Number of participants: ~50 Number of flyers: 75
Workshop	BDVA/ BDVF Steering Committee	07 February 2018	Brussels, Belgium	NTUA: Dimitris Askounis	Participation	n/a	H2020 Stakeholders	Awareness raising and knowledge exchange	Number of participants: 30
Exhibition and conference	Oceanology International	13-15 March 2018	London, United Kingdom	EXMILE: Dimitris Zisis, Konstantinos Chatzikokolak is	Interaction with industry communities and networks	http:// www.oceanologyinternational.com/	Maritime industry, academia, public sector and world's marine science and ocean technology communities	Ensure maximum visibility of the project, attract potential users/ clients	Number of participants: ~1000 Number of flyers: 200
Workshop	Big Mobility Data Analytics	26 March 2018		EXMILE: Konstantinos Chatzikokolak is	Presentation of a scientific paper	http://www.datastories.org/bmda18/	Academia and Research	Publication of project's results	n/a

Table I-3: Results from dissemination mechanism D3 "Scientific publications"

Type	Title	BigDataOcean related aspects	Link for publication
Project Networking session of the 14th Extended Semantic Web Conference (ESWC'17)	BigDataOcean - Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications	Presentation of the BigDataOcean project and pilots. Discussion and networking with other European research projects.	https://zenodo.org/record/815343#.WqrsbJPFJPU
Conference paper (23rd ICE/ITMC Conference)	Big data in power systems - leveraging grid optimisation and wave energy integration	Discussion on Big Data in power systems, with a special focus on "BigDataOcean wave power pilot".	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8279997/
Conference paper (23rd ICE/ITMC Conference)	Maritime data technology landscape and value chain - exploiting oceans of data for maritime applications	Discussion of maritime data technology landscape and value chain	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8280006/
Conference paper (23rd ICE/ITMC Conference)	A big data architecture for managing oceans of data and maritime applications	Presentation of the BigDataOcean architecture and concrete use cases based on the pilots. Discussion of challenges of a Big Data architecture for maritime data.	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8280019/
Conference paper (23rd ICE/ITMC Conference)	Intelligent security on the edge of the cloud	Anomaly Detection in real world vessel sensor streams	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8279999/
Workshop (Mobility Analytics for Spatio-temporal and Social Data (MATES2017))	A big data driven approach to extracting global trade patterns	Discussion on preliminary project results	https://zenodo.org/record/825825#.WqrK2pPFKnd
IEEE Big Data	Knowledge extraction from maritime spatiotemporal data: An evaluation of clustering algorithms on Big Data	Discussion on preliminary project results	http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8258106/
Big Mobility Data Analytics	Mining Vessel Trajectory Data for Patterns of Search and Rescue	Maritime Security and Anomaly Detection	https://zenodo.org/record/1203886#.WrDL6uhuY2w